

RESEARCH ON THE COMPOSITION OF NEW INNOVATIVE CONCRETES USED FOR ROAD PAVEMENTS AND THEIR PHYSICAL- MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

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Abstract: This article is dedicated to the study of the composition and physical-mechanical properties of new innovative concretes used for road pavements in modern transport infrastructure. Traditional concretes are prone to quick cracking and corrosion, making them vulnerable to extreme weather conditions. Innovative concretes aim to enhance quality through the use of additives and modifiers. The article discusses various types of innovative concretes, their physical-mechanical properties, and their applications in road pavements.

Keywords: Innovative concretes, Road pavements, Physical-mechanical properties, Traditional concrete, Corrosion resistance, Ecological concretes

In modern transport infrastructure, concrete pavements hold significant importance. As one of the main materials for roads, bridges, and other structures, concrete is distinguished by its high strength and long service life. However, traditional concrete has several drawbacks: it can quickly develop cracks, is prone to corrosion, and shows weakness against extreme weather conditions. Therefore, great emphasis is being placed on improving the quality of road pavements through the development of new components and innovative technologies added to concrete during scientific research.

Today, innovative concretes are being improved in various ways to enhance their physical and mechanical properties. These new technologies are primarily based on the use of additives and modifiers. These technologies serve to increase the corrosion resistance of pavements and enhance the heat, cold, and water permeability resistance of concrete.

The main goal of this article is to investigate the composition of innovative concretes and their advantages in road pavement applications. Within this framework, new types of concrete and their physical-mechanical properties will be analyzed, and practical recommendations will be provided based on the results of experimental research.

Traditional concretes consist of essential components such as water, cement, sand, and gravel. The mutual ratio and quality of these components are

the main factors determining the strength and durability of concrete. Traditional concretes have certain limitations, such as weaknesses in tension and bending, low corrosion resistance, and rapid damage under harsh weather conditions. These factors can reduce the service life of the concretes used in road pavements and increase operational costs.

Innovative concretes aim to eliminate the shortcomings of traditional concrete through new technologies and additives. For instance, nanoconcretes significantly enhance strength and durability with the help of nanomaterials. When nanomaterials are incorporated into the concrete mix, they improve the microstructure of the concrete, reduce cracks, and enhance corrosion resistance. Additionally, ecological concretes are also being developed, which are produced without harming the environment and are made from recycled materials.

Innovative concretes include high-strength fibers, polymer additives, and special chemical substances. Polymer concretes are highly resistant to severe chemical effects and corrosion, allowing for long service lives. Fiber-reinforced concretes significantly increase tensile and bending durability, which is crucial for road pavements. The composition of innovative concretes affects their physical-mechanical properties and provides essential characteristics for long-term use in road pavements.

The most important properties of innovative concretes are related to mechanical strength, elasticity, corrosion resistance, and durability against extreme weather conditions. Mechanical strength is determined by measuring the resistance of concrete to compressive, tensile, and bending forces. Nanomaterials, fibers, and polymers included in the composition of innovative concretes significantly improve these parameters.

The elastic modulus in bending measures the resistance of concrete to deformation. The fibers and polymers in the composition of innovative concretes add elasticity, which reduces the occurrence of cracks and increases strength. Additionally, this allows for better control of the level of deformation in concrete, which is critical for road pavements. Concretes produced using new technologies aim not to change shape under rapid cooling or heating effects.

Corrosion resistance is a crucial indicator that ensures the long-term usability of road pavements. Innovative concretes are reinforced with special chemicals and fibers to resist corrosion. Furthermore, water impermeability and freeze-thaw resistance are also of significant importance. Innovative concretes reduce the penetration of water into the concrete, thereby minimizing damage during freeze-thaw cycles.

Innovative concretes outperform traditional ones not only in mechanical properties but also in practical applications. In many countries, these types of concrete are widely used in the construction of bridges, tunnels, and road pavements. In projects utilizing innovative concrete, the strength and durability of road pavements significantly increase. For example, fiber-reinforced

concretes are widely used in bridges and roads that carry heavy loads due to their high resistance to tension.

Among the advantages of innovative concretes are their long service life, low maintenance requirements, and reduced operational costs. This makes infrastructure projects economically efficient. Additionally, these types of concrete are environmentally beneficial as they cause less harm to the environment and can be recycled.

Innovative concretes not only excel in mechanical and physical properties but also in practical applications compared to traditional concretes. The main task of road pavements is to provide a stable, safe, and long-lasting flow of vehicles. Furthermore, roads and other transport structures need to be resistant to corrosion, loads, and extreme weather conditions. Therefore, the concrete pavements used in road construction must have high quality and strength. Innovative concretes are emerging as one of the most effective solutions that meet these requirements.

Today, many countries are extensively using innovative concretes to renew and strengthen their infrastructure. These projects are being tested and successfully implemented on roads, bridges, tunnels, and airport runways. For instance:

Bridges and roads under heavy loads: Innovative concretes, particularly fiber and high-strength polymer concretes, are being used in bridge construction. These concretes can evenly distribute stress and have a long service life. For example, polymer concretes were used in the Bay Bridge project near San Francisco, USA, to enhance the durability of the bridge and reduce operational costs.

Tunnels and underground structures: High compressive strength and water-resistant concretes are required in underground structures. Nanoconcretes and fiber-reinforced concretes stand out here for their superior mechanical and waterproofing properties. In projects using innovative concretes, such as the construction of the Gotthard Base Tunnel in Switzerland, water-resistant and highly corrosion-resistant concretes were used

Airport runways: Innovative concretes are being applied in major airports. For instance, corrosion-resistant polymer concretes were used at Dubai International Airport to ensure the long-term usability of runways. The use of innovative concretes in airports makes them more resilient to the weight of aircraft and reduces the corrosion process.

The advantages of innovative concretes are multifaceted, offering numerous benefits for road pavements compared to traditional concretes. Below are the main advantages: **High strength:** Innovative concretes, particularly nanoconcretes and fiber-reinforced concretes, have high strength and can withstand heavy loads. This is critical for preventing cracks and settlements under the constant flow of vehicles and heavy trucks on road pavements.

Corrosion resistance: Innovative concretes, especially fiber and polymer concretes, have high resistance to corrosion. This ensures that the pavements remain intact for long periods without wear. For instance, as traffic density increases on roads, the level of corrosion also rises, leading to higher maintenance costs. Innovative concretes significantly reduce such corrosion.

Durability against extreme weather conditions: Innovative concretes show significant resilience to weather conditions. They perform much better in water, freeze, and thaw processes. Cracking due to freeze-thaw cycles is a major issue, especially in cold regions. Polymer and nanoconcretes reduce this process, increasing the long-term usability of road pavements.

Fast curing and quick installation: Another important advantage of innovative concretes is their rapid curing ability. In road construction, speed is often crucial, as keeping roads closed for long periods negatively impacts traffic flow. Nanoconcretes and polymer concretes cure quickly and can be put to use in a short time.

Reduced maintenance and operational costs: Due to the long service life of innovative concretes, repair and maintenance costs for road pavements can be significantly reduced. Their lower susceptibility to cracks and other damages leads to lower operational costs, resulting in substantial economic benefits over the long term.

Due to the high-tech processes and special materials used in their production, innovative concretes may have a higher initial cost than traditional concretes. However, in the long run, the economic efficiency of innovative concretes becomes evident. This can be explained as follows:

Long service life: Innovative concretes last longer than traditional ones, reducing the need for frequent repairs of roads. For instance, in many countries, the rapid deterioration of roads, especially their susceptibility to corrosion and cracking, is a significant problem. Innovative concretes help address this issue, as they exhibit higher durability against corrosion and mechanical damage.

Low maintenance requirements: The high durability of innovative concretes ensures the long-term preservation of road pavements. This significantly reduces maintenance and repair costs. For example, roads constructed with fiber-reinforced concretes are less prone to cracks and other damages, resulting in fewer repair works.

Reduced repair works and road closures: The fast curing properties of innovative concretes facilitate quick repairs and their prompt availability for use. This helps maintain the stability of traffic flow and reduces delays and congestion in the transport system.

Energy efficiency: Some types of innovative concretes, such as ecological concretes, consume less energy during the production process and do not emit harmful gases into the environment. This increases their ecological efficiency.

Eco-friendly concretes produced from recycled materials help reduce the overall energy consumption of transport infrastructure.

In the future, innovative concretes are expected to be used even more widely in road construction. The demand for new technologies and environmentally safe materials is increasing in the development and strengthening of transport infrastructure worldwide.

Innovative concretes are demonstrating themselves not only as technologically advanced solutions but also as economically viable options. Additionally, their ecological cleanliness and sustainability are of significant importance for future transport systems

Ecological concretes: The use of ecological concretes is expected to rise in the future. Such concretes are produced with the help of recycled materials, bio-polymers, and other environmentally friendly additives. This helps reduce the ecological footprint of road construction..

Advancements in construction technologies: The further development and expansion of innovative concretes are closely linked to improvements in construction technologies. With 3D printing technology and other modern methods, the rapid and efficient construction of concrete structures can be achieved.

Economic efficiency and long-term use: Innovative concretes ensure the long service life of roads, allowing for effective allocation of funds targeted at infrastructure by reducing operational costs.

In conclusion, innovative concretes are proving to be a viable alternative to traditional concretes in road pavements. The research demonstrates that new types of concrete possess improved physical-mechanical properties and offer significant advantages for their application. Their high strength, corrosion resistance, durability, and low maintenance requirements make innovative concretes an important factor for the future of road construction.

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